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COMPARATIVE PROFITABILITY ASSESSMENT OF PV + BESS FOR DIFFERENT CONFIGURATIONS AND BUSINESS MODELS

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ABSTRACT: The critical need for storage in an energy system going in the direction of 100% renewable is well acknowledged. Important battery prices decrease and access to additional revenue streams have been key reasons to consider projects combining PV and BESS (Battery Energy Storage System). In this paper, three PV+BESS study cases are investigated: SC1: provision of ancillary services and arbitrage, SC2: electricity supply in off-grid/remote areas, SC3: self-consumption increase. First, the cost competitiveness of these study cases is evaluated using the Net Present Value, then it is compared to that of a similar PV-only project. This not only allows to determine whether PV+BESS projects can be profitable but also whether the additional revenues and savings generated thanks to the BESS compensate for the additional investment, operation and maintenance costs. Results show that with current electricity and BESS prices, PV + BESS can lead to very competitive investments in SC2 or to investments close to break-even in SC1 and SC3. In general, likely future trends (e.g., decreasing battery prices, decreasing incentives for electricity fed to the grid, diminishing average selling prices for utility-scale PV, ...) should strengthen PV+BESS cases.

Keywords: Storage, PV, Competitiveness, Profitability

1 INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we provide an overview of the level of competitiveness of PV + BESS (Battery Energy Storage System) projects under three configurations. The BESS technology hypothesized is Lithium-ion.

The competitiveness assessment and profitability evaluation of each study case look at both a PV-only configuration and a PV + BESS hybrid project. This allows us to determine whether the additional revenues and savings generated thanks to the BESS compensate for the additional investment and operation and maintenance costs. Several indicators are used to quantitatively describe the study cases. In all cases, the net present value (NPV) is calculated. When relevant, additional indicators such as the self-sufficiency rate, the self-consumption rate or the avoided CO₂ emissions are also calculated.

2 METHODOLOGY

Three projects under three configurations were considered for the analysis:

- (1) Large-scale PV + BESS project providing ancillary services and arbitrage (SC1);
- (2) Large-scale PV + BESS project complementing fossil fuel-based electricity supply in off-grid/remote areas (SC2);
- (3) Rooftop PV + BESS project aiming at increasing self-consumption (SC3).

The main assumptions made on the PV and BESS are illustrative of typical configurations observed for the considered applications and derived from real project reviews.

The hypothesized SC1 is a ground-mounted PV system with 25 MWp in Germany. In the PV-only configuration, the revenues come from the selling of electricity on the wholesale market. In the PV + BESS configuration, a BESS of 25 MW/25 MWh is added. The additional revenues from the BESS are distributed between the participation of the storage unit in Frequency Containment Reserve (FCR) services as well as arbitrage.

In the SC2, a ground-mounted PV system is hypothesized in Faial Island, Azores, Portugal, to substitute part of the fossil fuel energy supply in the island (off-grid system). The PV system considered in the PV-only case has a power capacity of 10 MWp. In the PV+BESS case, thanks to the addition of a BESS (5 MW/20 MWh), the PV installed capacity can be increased to 20 MWp. In both PV and PV+BESS cases, the revenues come from the avoided fuel consumption.

For SC3, an industrial facility located in Belgium equipped with a 500 kWp PV system and self-consumption is considered. In the PV+BESS configuration, a BESS with a size of 250 kW/1000 kWh is added. The main source of revenues in both cases comes from the savings on the electricity bill through self-consumption. With the BESS, the self-consumption rate is increased, therefore, increasing the electricity savings. Part of the production is still injected into the grid, which represents an additional revenue.

Table I: Considered three study cases' description.

Study case ID	SC1	SC2	SC3
PV system	cSi, ground-mounted, south oriented	cSi, ground-mounted, south oriented	cSi, rooftop, south oriented
Location	Germany	Portugal (Azores)	Belgium
PV system size	25 MW	10 MW (PV only) 20 MW (PV+BESS)	500 kW
BESS size*	25 MW/25 MWh	11 MW/45 MWh	125 kW/500 kWh
Hybrid business model	Sale on the wholesale market merchant-PV), arbitrage and FCR provision	Reduction of fossil fuel-based electricity generation	Savings on the electricity bill through (increased) self-consumption
Reference business model	Sale on the wholesale market (merchant PV)	Reduction of fossil fuel-based electricity generation	Savings on the electricity bill through self-consumption

* illustrative of typical configuration observed for the considered applications and derived from real projects review

The main assumptions used for the PV and BESS systems in the study cases are provided in **Table II** [2] [3] [4]. The considered BESS technology is Li-ion. Li-ion is the dominant electrochemical storage technology with around 90% market share [1]. More specifically, the considered chemistry is LFP (Lithium Iron Phosphate) as they are less expensive and can perform safely at higher temperatures while their lower volumetric energy density is not a barrier for stationary applications. Li-ion technology advancement allows a lifetime of 15 years and a round-trip efficiency of 90% [5].

Table II: Main system assumptions for the study cases

Study case ID	SC1	SC2	SC3
PV CAPEX [€/Wp]	0,65	0,7	0,8
PV OPEX [€/kWp.a]	15	15	10
PV yield [kWh/kWp]	1196	1322	1026
Revenue sources [€/MWh]	FCR price: 92; Arbitrage: 120 Merchant-PV: 82	Avoided fuel cost: 240	Self-consumed energy: 130 Injection: 80
Round-trip efficiency [%]		90	
Lifetime [years]		15	
BESS CAPEX [€/kWh]	433	391	444
BESS OPEX [€/kWh.a]		1,5% of CAPEX	

The PV production time series for these PV systems and respective locations were obtained using PVGIS online tool, these time series have a duration of 1 year [6]. In SC1, the value of FCR provision was obtained using 2021 auction results [7]. In SC2, the fuel cost was calculated based on the fixed price of fuel by the Azorean Regional Government as of September 2023. In SC3, average retail electricity prices for commercial and industrial customers were used. [8] Eventually, wholesale electricity prices hourly time series from 2021 were used [9].

The financial parameters chosen for the assessment of profitability and competitiveness in all study cases are indicated in **Table III**.

Table III: Financial parameters assumptions

Parameters	Financial assumptions
Cost of equity [%]	8
Annual inflation [%]	2,5
Corporate tax rate [%]	25
Debt financing [%]	80

Although PV systems largely outlive 15 years, the BESS average lifetime of 15 years is taken to calculate the net present value. This allows us to determine whether it is profitable or not to consider the addition of a BESS to a PV system at the time of its installation.

3 RESULTS

The profitability is first assessed under current boundary conditions, both for a PV only and a PV+BESS configuration. Then a sensitivity analysis is conducted to visualize the influence of different BESS CAPEX and different energy market conditions on the profitability of PV+BESS projects.

3.1 SC1: Large-scale PV+BESS project providing ancillary services and arbitrage

Figure 1: Competitiveness assessment of SC1 under current boundary conditions.

Figure 2: Competitiveness assessment of SC1 under a range of boundary conditions.

With the base case assumptions, the addition of a storage system allows to generate additional revenues from arbitrage and FCR provision. Yet, additional costs outweigh the additional revenues, and the NPV is deteriorated compared to the case with PV-only. Still, break-even is reached.

Looking at other boundary conditions related to BESS CAPEX and the gap between merchant PV revenues and FCR revenues allows to identify that a 10% BESS CAPEX decrease can already enable a positive NPV for the PV+BESS configuration. Higher gaps between PV revenues and FCR revenues can also benefit the PV+BESS business case. These can be a result of either higher need for ancillary services provision and/or lower selling prices for merchant PV. While the latter is a likely evolution in the coming years with higher PV and renewables' penetration, FCR revenues have rather been decreasing due to BESS market saturation, but aFRR provision is an equivalent, a relevant and an attractive alternative with less fierce competition.

3.2 SC2: Large-scale PV+BESS project complementing fossil fuel-based electricity (off-grid)

Figure 3: Competitiveness assessment of SC2 under current boundary conditions.

Figure 4: Competitiveness assessment of SC2 under a range of boundary conditions

With the base case assumptions, the addition of a storage system allows to displace larger quantities of fossil fuels and offset the associated CO₂ emissions. Even if the PV+BESS ensures electricity supply at a higher cost compared to a PV-only configuration, there are several advantages to the hybrid configuration. First, with the addition of storage, the PV installed capacity and with it renewable penetration can be higher which also allows larger quantities of avoided fossil fuel and as a direct result, larger quantities of avoided CO₂ emissions (17 vs. 9 kton of CO₂ per year). In addition, the hybrid combination ensures the security of supply and a predictable cost of electricity thus hedging against important fossil fuel price variations.

Looking at alternative boundary conditions related to the price of electricity from fossil fuel generators, it can be seen how less pessimistic assumptions compared to the base case can even further strengthen the case (e.g., also considering non-fuel related costs such as the initial investment in and installation and maintenance of the fossil fuel generator).

3.3 SC3: Rooftop PV+BESS project aiming at increasing self-consumption

Figure 5: Competitiveness assessment of SC3 under current boundary conditions

Figure 6: Competitiveness assessment of SC3 under a range of boundary conditions

With the base case assumptions, the addition of a storage system allows to increase the revenues from self-consumption (increase from a rate of 60% in the PV-only configuration vs. 79% in the PV+BESS configuration). Yet, additional costs outweigh the additional revenues, and the NPV deteriorated compared to the case with PV-only. Still, break-even is almost reached. Even if the PV+BESS project under base case assumption is poorly profitable, self-sufficiency is increased by 10pp, which enables a predictable cost of electricity for a higher share of the electricity demand thus hedging against electricity price variation and volatility.

Looking at other boundary conditions related to BESS CAPEX allows us to identify that a 10% BESS CAPEX decrease can already enable a positive NPV for the PV+BESS configuration. Eventually, increasing gaps between self-consumption PV revenues and the revenues from the injection of surplus electricity also have the potential to strengthen the hybrid case, driven by shrinking remuneration for surplus electricity.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Hybrid PV+BESS can lead to very competitive investments in one of the considered study case (SC2: large-scale PV+BESS project complementing fossil fuel-based electricity supply in off-grid/remote areas) or to investment close to break-even in two of the considered study cases (SC1: large-scale PV+BESS project providing ancillary services (FCR: frequency containment reserve) and SC3: C&I rooftop PV+BESS project aiming at increasing self-consumption) with current electricity and BESS prices.

Yet, if hybrid PV+BESS projects can be competitive, they currently often lead to a lower profitability level compared to a PV-only configuration.

Key enablers to improve the economic interest of hybrid projects are BESS prices as well as energy market trends. In general, likely future trends should strengthen PV+BESS cases. One can mention (i) battery prices which are foreseen to keep on decreasing; (ii) incentives for electricity fed to the grid (i.e., not self-consumed) that are decreasing or even being phased out; (iii) average selling prices for utility-scale PV which could diminish and (iv) the need from ancillary services' provision which should increase with rising renewable penetration rates.

Eventually, beyond the purely economic considerations presented here, additional aspects such as (i) security of supply, (ii) resilience to energy prices' volatility, (iii) increasing renewable penetration and (iv) avoided fossil-fuel-related emissions can be mentioned as further drivers of the attractiveness of hybrid PV+BESS systems.

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